

Scientific article

Towards a load surrogate model for low-frequency fatigue cycles in wind turbines

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Abstract: *Load surrogates have emerged as efficient tools for fatigue analysis of wind turbines (WTs) in applications such as site assessment, wind farm control, and lifetime extension. They map 10-minute WT-specific inflow and operating conditions to damage equivalent loads (DELs), typically calculated using standard half-cycle rainflow counting. Fatigue damage is accumulated statistically, while low-frequency fatigue cycles (LFFCs) beyond the 10-minute interval –caused by low-frequency turbulence, diurnal and seasonal variations, and operating state transitions– are typically neglected or only partially captured. These LFFCs include some of the largest and most damaging fatigue cycles experienced by WTs. This study takes a preliminary step towards the extension of conventional load surrogate models to account for LFFCs by reconstructing the long-term residual time series using residual parameters estimated by the surrogate. The methodology is applied to tower-base measurements from a real onshore WT, and surrogate performance is evaluated over multiple reference periods. The sensitivity to different choices for the residual parameters is investigated, leading to the identification of the best performing option. The proposed extension of the conventional load surrogates enables future LFFC-aware wind farm optimization and lifetime-extension applications.*

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